

THE CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL APPROACH TO CLIMATE SECURITY: EVOLUTION FROM UNKNOWN TO EXISTENTIAL ISSUE

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Abstract

Natural conditions have always determined human existence. Climate, as some authors suggest, will lead warmer regions towards democracy while peoples from colder regions will be determined towards more autocratic rule. However, the most serious problem arises when natural disasters and climate crises make life impossible and devalue it, whether it is more democratic or autocratic. Droughts and floods lead to food and water shortages and new conflicts. The most vulnerable categories of society suffer the greatest consequences, which leads to instability and new migrations. This results in a large number of communities struggling to survive. Dealing with the consequences of climate change and disasters known under the term climate security raises the issue of the constitutional approach to it, which, appreciating the maxim *lex prospicit, non respicit*, must provide an up-to-date answer and set new guidelines in the legal and security order. The transition of this issue from a purely ecological to an existential issue elevates it to the position of a constitutional and security matter. Failure to recognize this concept will not only violate the rights and freedoms of current generations, but will also deprive future, unborn generations of the right to live in a safe and dignified environment. The constitutional and legal history of climate security brings an evolution that leads to clear legal recognition, emphasizing nevertheless judicial activism as crucial in bureaucratized systems.

Keywords: climate security, constitutional law, environmental law, climate change, constitutionalization

1. INTRODUCTION

When the environment experiences alarming and tectonic disturbances faced with unstoppable degrading processes, humanity has an obligation to stop the spiral of collapse, because otherwise – any life without conditions is a mere illusion. The data are more than worrying: the Amazon rainforest has already lost over 17% of its surface in the last 50 years, and over 50% of the world's coral reefs are dead or irreversibly damaged. Glaciers lose more than 600 billion tons of ice per year. The decline in pollinators directly threatens about 75% of agricultural production.

In the eyes of the insufficiently informed public, climate change seems like a phenomenon that is distant, that affects distant countries, that is not directly responsible for the emergence of emergencies, forced migrations and that does not pose a direct threat to any segment of human life. The reality is different (Simić, 2019, p. 41).

Climate change and disasters are no longer exclusively an ecological issue, but represent an existential challenge for the survival of society. What was previously unknown, in the 21st century is growing into a dominant and central issue of law and security. Climate security combines the concepts of environment and climate change, placing them in relation to human and global security, which raises the question of how constitutional systems respond to these threats? In a constellation of relations dominated by conflicts and migrations, security is violated, constitutional law is faced with the challenge of how to accept the concept of *salus publica suprema lex esto*¹⁰ – according to which the public good is the supreme law.

With the growth of European colonialism, the theory dedicated to climatic determinism¹¹ will serve as a "fig leaf"¹² to justify racism, eugenic policies and imperialism. From the 19th¹³ to the 20th century we record the greatest abuses of the climate, which through scientific racism and pseudoscience will legitimize colonial campaigns and slavery. In the last century Hitler, inspired by Haushofer's concept of Lebensraum – a natural right to expansion, will introduce the world to new wars and genocides. It is precisely this epilogue that will lead to a strong criticism of this type of determinism, which in the 21st century brings a new form of climate security. In contemporary concepts, we have a reconnection of man and nature (climate), but not as a justification or abuse, but in the direction of responsibility and an ethical approach. The transition from "climate that creates man" to "man who creates climate unsafe conditions" is already being noticed.

Climate security denotes the degree of systemic and institutional resilience of the order in conditions of climate instability. It represents a continuity in which the state is able to preserve its constitutional identity and social development, despite the escalation of climate risks that disrupt the natural and economic balance. Climate security is a new, modern social contract of the state and citizens with nature, in which a legal system is created as a resilient mechanism, and of course accompanied by a redefinition of relations in society.

The constitutionalization of climate security in the 21st century, which represents a new stage in constitutional evolution, through the transition from a political declaration to a constitutional guarantee, recognizes climate as the foundation of human dignity and the constitutional-legal system. The European continent is leading the process of

¹⁰ A Latin phrase originally used by Cicero, in order to emphasize that the interest of the state and the public should stand above personal or party interests.

¹¹ Geographical or ecological determinism is a theory according to which the natural environment, i.e. climate, geography, relief and resources, influence the development of society, culture and even the character of people. Ecological determinism shows a strong connection between nature and man, something that is again being actualized in this concept.

¹² The phrase "fig leaf" figuratively refers to something that conceals shame or guilt, a symbol for false concealment. As an expression, it comes from the Bible, specifically from the Book of Genesis 3:7, according to which "Then the eyes of both of them were opened, and they knew that they were naked; and they sewed fig leaves together and made themselves aprons". In Renaissance art, the leaf was often used to censor nudity. It is known that fig leaves were later added to some of Michelangelo's sculptures to depict modesty.

¹³ In the USA we have the concept of Manifest Destiny which claimed that they have a natural and divine right to expand their territory "from sea to sea".

constitutionalization, and European constitutional courts often compensate for the passivity of the legislative and executive branches.

This paper, through a comparative legal analysis, presents the evolutionary path of climate security, which from an unknown and ecological issue to an existential issue becomes a constitutional matter.

2. HISTORICAL AND THEORETICAL CONTEXT

2.1 Climate and security throughout history

The historical understanding of climate has evolved through different stages. The flood that we encounter in the “Epic of Gilgamesh” and later in the biblical story of Noah’s Ark represents the first climatic catastrophe that serves as a punishment for human corruption and immorality that disrupted the balance of nature and the gods.

Later, in the Code of Hammurabi, we already note the first provisions on irrigation systems, floods and droughts. In the provisions, we notice the first legal text that treats natural disasters as a legal consequence.

Hippocrates, the author after whom the most famous medical oath is named, in the work “Airs, Waters, and Places” first connects climate with the character and health of nations. Security in this context refers to the physical survival of the community. Aristotle, through his works “Politics” and “Meteorology”, connects climatic conditions with political order. According to him, climate affects the form of government and social morality.

In the Roman period, the concept of *res communes omnium* develops, which refers to the common goods of all (water, air, sea). Nature here becomes a legal category.

In the Middle Ages, natural disasters and climate change are considered divine punishment. Security in this time interval is perceived from a religious and moral aspect. Thomas Aquinas builds on Aristotle's work and Roman law, but introduces a Christian theological character. According to him, the law arises from the eternal law of God, and man must preserve that order, which also includes nature.

In the period of enlightenment, in the authors Montesquieu and Rousseau, we note the connection of climate with questions of moral balance and social stability, derived through the prism of the new political and legal orders of that time.

The period of the Industrial Revolution saw climate as a means of economic and imperial power. Industrial expansion led to enormous pollution, disease, and resource instability. After the mass pollutions in London, Manchester, and Paris, the process of passing laws that accepted the idea of state responsibility for nature was evident. The Public Health Act (1848, Great Britain) and the Forest Service (1905, USA) are examples of such anticipation. This period will also be known for the fact that many authors, including Thomas Jefferson, used environmental determinism to support and legitimize African colonization, arguing that tropical climates made people uncivilized.

In World War II, nature was slowly but surely brought into the realm of global security, in response to major environmental disasters and nuclear threats. The second half of the 20th century is particularly significant, as we see a growing number of international documents that enable the later acceptance of climate security (which will ultimately lead

to its constitutionalization¹⁴). Perhaps the most revolutionary impact will be achieved by the Stockholm Declaration of 1972, which will be reaffirmed and strengthened by the Rio de Janeiro Declaration of 1992. In 1987, the Brundtland Report will introduce the concept of sustainable development.

The 21st century, from its very beginning, heralds a kind of "golden age" for climate security. In 2007, the UN Security Council discussed climate as a security threat for the first time. The 2015 Paris Agreement, on the other hand, recognizes that climate change is a threat to human rights and global security. These key events will quickly multiply the new notion of security, and international organizations such as UNDP and IPCC will warn that climate crises lead to new conflicts, migrations and political instability. Climate is becoming an existential threat.

One of the most serious threats to humanity today and the leading security challenge in the world is climate change caused by global warming (Udovčić, 2024, p. 1).

2.2 The international character of climate security and its dependence on international law

One of the main characteristics of climate security is its international character, as well as its direct dependence on the development of international law. This concept is an example of a "top-down" concept, which is first developed internationally, and then these provisions are transposed into domestic legal systems.

Hugo Grotius' idea of *ius gentium* (law of nations) and *res communis* (common goods) creates a notion of global order, which has as a consequence the subsequent regulation of global resources and the environment. Although he does not mention climate and climate security directly, the principles he sets out will form the intellectual and legal basis for the concept of climate security. Grotius' elaborated principle "*sic utere tuo ut alienum non laedas*" which translates to "use your own so that you do not harm others", refers to the prohibition of causing harm to other states or common global goods, and was formalized as principle 21 of the 1972 Stockholm Declaration (also confirmed in the 1992 Rio Declaration).

We see the principle of common but differentiated responsibility in the 2015 Paris Agreement, which follows the logic of *res communis omnium*. This type of security today is not only a matter of protecting nature and the climate, but also of peace and global order, which is the essential message of Grotius' work "*De Jure Belli ac Pacis*" (1625).

In 1987, in the Brundtland Commission Report, we have the introduction of the concept of sustainable development, which connects the environment and global stability. This was followed by the 1992 UN Climate Change Convention, which was the first global framework for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Of course, the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, which introduced legally binding targets for industrialized countries, is also important in this context.

The UN Security Council, for the first time in 2007, considered climate change as a potential threat to peace and security. Climate change and its risks were directly linked to

¹⁴ Constitutionalization is a process in which certain rights, norms, principles, values, or areas are elevated to the level of constitutional matter, giving them the highest degree of state and social protection. The term constitutionalism was coined in 1832 by the English poet R. Southey; along with English legal writers, O. Gierke is particularly responsible for its acceptance as a professional term. More: <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/konstitucionalizam>

food shortages¹⁵, which lead to migration and conflict, as well as to natural disasters, which lead to humanitarian crises and new instability.

The 2015 Paris Agreement set a goal of limiting global warming to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels, with efforts to limit it to 1.5°C. The agreement aims to reduce the risks and consequences of climate change, which include climate disasters, migration, conflict and food and water shortages. The agreement recognizes climate change as a threat to peace and stability. The agreement also accepts that the countries that have historically contributed the most to climate change bear the greatest responsibility, while advocating solidarity with smaller and less developed countries, which are disproportionately affected by this threat.

2.2.1 European Union

In 2008, the EU, in the Climate and Energy Package, acknowledged that climate change affects security. Later, in 2013, the European Security Strategy (ESS) Update first mentioned climate change as a factor in global instability and a risk to peace. The 2016 EU Global Strategy (EUGS), for example, stated that climate change is a threat to security, while also creating new migration and conflicts. A particular step forward was noted in 2019 with the European Green Deal (a policy of climate neutrality by 2050 was introduced) and the EU Climate Diplomacy Action Plan of 2020, which integrated climate security into EU foreign policy, especially in the area of stabilization for Africa and the Middle East.

However, given the common goals and threats posed by climate change, cooperation between the EU and the USA remains crucial for global climate security¹⁶.

2.2.2 NATO

With regard to NATO, in 2009 we have the first official document linking climate to security. The following year, the Strategic Concept 2010 already acknowledged that climate change could cause instability in geopolitical frameworks and affect operations. Perhaps the most explicit recognition of climate security and its consequences is in the NATO Climate Change and Security Action Plan from 2021, which presents a concrete strategy for adapting bases, preparing for extreme weather conditions and integrating climate risks into mission planning.

2.3 Theoretical considerations on climate security

¹⁵ The World Food Programme (WFP) has made a worrying assessment that more than 80% of the world's food-insecure population live in countries with degraded environments prone to natural disasters. When climate-related events occur, the situation of already vulnerable people can quickly deteriorate, leading to famine. The problems of acute food insecurity and malnutrition are exacerbated where natural hazards such as droughts and floods are compounded by the effects of conflict. An example of such a situation is the Horn of Africa, where the rainy season failed for the first time in 2016. See Milosavljević (2019) for more details.

¹⁶ Is an international climate regime possible? Based on the research on realpolitik relations between states in the period between the Rio summits of 1992 and 2012, it seems that it is not. However, the essence of the problem is not mistrust between states or pragmatic exploitation of the situation for their own benefit (in which China is at the forefront), but the fact that economic development and the world market as such are the negation of climate awareness. For further discussion, see Popović (2014).

After the 1990s, we have seen a significant expansion of the concept of security. Especially after the Cold War, securitization has also encompassed new threats, which also incorporate the moment of nature and climate. The Copenhagen School has proven to be crucial, introducing the idea that climate and migration can be recognized as security threats.

In 1994, the UNDP introduced the framework for "human security", and as an integral part it includes ecological and climate stability.

The traditional (realist) approach to climate change sees it as a "threat multiplier". According to Thomas Homer-Dixon, known for his work "Environment, Scarcity and Violence" (1999), the lack of resources leads to conflicts.

Representatives of the liberal-institutional approach, such as Oran R. Young (author of "The Institutional Dimensions of Environmental Change: Fit, Interplay, and Scale"), emphasize the role of international institutions in dealing with climate risks and the need for global coordination.

Brauch and Hans Günter, as representatives of the human, social approach to climate security, cite climate as a human security issue.

3. CONCEPT AND FUNCTION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

Climate security is a new, interdisciplinary concept that connects the security, legal, political and economic dimensions of climate change. It is a state of protection of society, the state and nature from the risks and consequences of climate change (in order to preserve stability, health and international peace).

Problems with droughts, lack of food and water, floods, migrations and conflicts over resources, lead to a strong introduction of climate risks into national security strategies, because they are accepted as a threat to national and international security.

On the international level, this type of security is already integrated into international agreements, and is already widely accepted within the framework of the UN, the Security Council, the EU, NATO and others.

In terms of the legal function, climate security has the task of offering judicial protection and climate obligations (followed, of course, by its gradual constitutionalization). In terms of its function towards society, this type of security is aimed at human and social stability, and its function is to ensure climate justice¹⁷.

Especially after the major environmental disasters of the last century and after World War II, the need to include the environment in security is undeniable. The Cold War period requires an approach to security with a more rational and realpolitik approach, which would include elements that are not just part of the traditional understanding. The concept of environmental security was particularly developed in the 1960s and was accepted under that name 20 years later (Koprivnjak & Vidaček, 2024, p.162).

4. CONSTITUTIONAL-LEGAL DIMENSION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

4.1 Constitutional law as a traditional discipline

¹⁷ The term climate justice began to be used in the late 1980s, then within the framework of the environmental justice movement in the United States. It was first used by activists of African Americans and indigenous communities, who pointed out that environmental risks (especially waste and pollution) are concentrated in wider areas. Theoretical formulations for this term can be seen around 2002 by Mary Robinson, former president of Ireland.

Constitutional law has long been the subject of the odium of a conservative, traditional discipline that specifically accepts changes around it. Such a remark is quite justified, considering that initially and theoretically it defends and develops classical political rights, the subject of which is power and limitations.

Especially on the example of Great Britain we can see more of a classical conservative constitutional tradition, which does not know a constitution in written form, as a systematized act, but is a collection of several acts, judicial precedents and constitutional conventions and customs. In this way, the stability of the order is valued (which is both the basic function and task of constitutional law), and changes come along an evolutionary path, not through radical upheavals.

If the basic function of constitutional law is to maintain order, stability and security, then it must undoubtedly include the latest risks to life and well-being. It is in this field that the role of security is also seen, which together with constitutional law functions according to the principle of a coin with two sides.

As a counterweight to the popular originalism theory¹⁸ (according to which the constitution is strictly interpreted according to the will of the first framers of the constitution) the theory of the Constitution as a Living Constitution¹⁹, i.e. as *materia viva*²⁰, according to which it lives and develops with society.

4.2 Judicial Activism

Judicial activism as a legal doctrine and practice refers to judges who actively intervene in social and moral issues through their actions. The term was first used by Arthur Schlesinger Jr. in 1947, who used it to describe the US Supreme Court during the so-called Warren Court (1953–1969), whose composition actively protected human and civil rights. Under the leadership of Earl Warren, the court made a series of historic decisions. In the case of *Brown v. Board of Education* (1954), the principle of "separate but equal" was overturned and racial segregation in public schools was prohibited (which violated the 14th Amendment, which concerns equal protection under the law).

Furthermore, in 1961, under the leadership of Warren, in the case of *Mapp v. Ohio*, the Supreme Court decided that evidence obtained from an illegal search may not be used in court. In 1966, the Supreme Court, through its ruling in the case of *Miranda v. Arizona*, introduced the famous "Miranda rights" that refer to the obligation of the police to inform the accused of his rights upon arrest.

In this way, with its engagement (or rather activism²¹), the court has redefined American democracy, in a way that introduces new standards for freedom, equality and human rights.

¹⁸ Originalism is a legal theory according to which the constitution should be interpreted according to its original meaning or intention at the time of adoption. The main advocates in history are several American Supreme Court justices. The focus is on the text and historical context.

¹⁹ Contrary to the theory of the originalists, the theory of the Living Constitution is developing in the USA. Similar to the European version, the constitution as *materia viva*.

²⁰ The theory according to which the Constitution is *materia viva*, as a metaphor for the living, dynamic character of the constitution. The interpretation of the constitution is carried out according to contemporary needs and values. It originates from European soil, especially France and Italy. It is a counterbalance to traditional positivist constitutional law (following the example of Kelsen).

²¹ More in Ceranić (2010).

The theory of living constitutionality, accompanied by judicial activism as its emanation, creates a modern constitutional practice in which the constitution is not changed only through amendments, but constitutional courts, through extensive and dynamic interpretation, play an active role in the protection of freedoms and rights. They create an evolutionary and dynamic system from a static, traditional and conservative discipline of constitutional law. However, constitutional law has its own ability to independently complement and upgrade itself.

4.3 Climate trials before constitutional and supreme courts

Although the Netherlands does not have a constitutional court in the classical sense (as established in 1920, with the first Kelsen²² court in Austria²³), the judgment in the case *Urgenda v. Netherlands* (2019) shows how the Supreme Court protects constitutional principles even without having a formal constitutional status. This is a case in which the Urgenda Foundation sued the Dutch state for failure to fulfil its obligation to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. The Supreme Court, as the highest court, has ordered the state to reduce emissions by at least 25% by 2020 compared to 1990. This is actually the first case where a supreme court has ordered a state to take specific climate action, thereby indirectly exercising a constitutional function and setting an important legal precedent in terms of climate protection.

In the case *Neubauer v. Germany*, the German Federal Constitutional Court ruled on 24 March 2021 that part of the Federal Climate Protection Act (*Klimaschutzgesetz*) is unconstitutional because it “does not sufficiently protect people from future violations and restrictions of their freedoms as climate change intensifies”. The plaintiffs, including Laura Neubauer, have argued that the law’s goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 is insufficient and does not protect their fundamental rights, such as the right to life²⁴, health and liberty. By ruling, the court recognizes climate rights, thereby accepting climate protection as part of fundamental rights (which also include the right to life and health). The court has emphasized the state’s obligation to protect the fundamental rights of future generations. In doing so, the court imposes an obligation to revise the legislation in order to ensure that emissions are as low as possible.

5. CONSTITUTIONALIZATION OF CLIMATE SECURITY

5.1 From unknown, through ecological, to existential issue

Until the middle of the last century, climate and climate change were practically unknown to the mainstream course in security sciences. Nature is a resource, and is perceived as such, but not as a factor that influences the types of security.

After the 1970s of the 21st century, when the process of constitutional acceptance of provisions on environmental law began, climate change began to be treated as an environmental issue and threat. The period from the 1980s to around 2000 can be spoken of as a kind of pre-period of green constitutionalism (considering that we already have acceptance of principles such as sustainable development, etc.).

Green constitutionalism, as a hybrid model between human rights, state obligations and environmental protection, is becoming a serious tendency in constitutional

²² More in Marković (2023).

²³ More in Kijevčanin (2022).

²⁴ More in Orlović (2014).

law in the 21st century. Climate security is an integral part of it, because otherwise this type of security cannot function in isolation. As stated in Vidacek and Ristovska (2025), green constitutionalism brings a much more mature and modern perspective – ecocentric, which elevates ecological sustainability above human needs.

5.2 Direct constitutionalization

With Amendment 20A to the German Basic Law (Grundgesetz), “the state, also in its responsibility towards future generations, shall protect the natural foundations of life and animals within the framework of the constitutional order, through legislation and, in accordance with law and justice, through the executive and judicial branches.” With this, since 1993, environmental protection has been directly rooted in German constitutional law. The court has used this as the basis for the Nuebauer v. Germany judgment from 2021.

Here we have a situation in which a right, or value, is explicitly inserted into the constitutional text (by means of new articles, amendments or a separate chapter, depending on the constitutional legal system and nomotechnics).

In terms of the strict mention of the term climate security, one should mention the case of France, 2021²⁵, when the request "to combat climate change" was proposed, but not fully adopted. Such possible acceptance would mean direct, explicit recognition of climate change in the Constitution. In the absence of such constitutionalization, one moves on to other forms of constitutionalization.

5.3 Indirect and judicial constitutionalization

When constitutional or supreme courts (with constitutional jurisdiction) interpret constitutional norms and through their actions create new constitutional law or expand the content of the existing one, it is judicial constitutionalization, which in turn is part of the broader concept of indirect constitutionalization.

This can be concluded that not every indirect constitutionalization is judicial. Following the example of Germany, there the constitutional doctrine has long before the courts accepted that human dignity has a material constitutional character. This is a broader concept because it can encompass a broader political and scientific interpretation, which is not always related to the court.

Indirect constitutionalization in general, especially in the area of climate security, is the most common. This is a situation in which although the right or value is not explicitly stated in the constitution, it is derived from existing constitutional norms, principles or case law.

If we look back at a Norwegian case from 2020, we see that the Norwegian constitution, in Article 112, states "Natural resources shall be managed on the basis of comprehensive long-term considerations that will protect this right for future generations", which is what the Supreme Court of Sweden referred to when advocating the state's obligation to prevent climate damage (Greenpeace Norway v. Ministry of Petroleum).

5.4 Other types of constitutionalization

²⁵ Following a proposal by the Convention citoyenne pour le climat, composed of 150 citizens, an amendment to Article 1 of the French constitution was proposed, according to which "The Republic guarantees the preservation of the environment and biological diversity and combats climate change". Although the lower house accepted the proposed amendment with 391 votes "for", 47 "against", in the further procedure a common text was not agreed upon.

The content of the preamble and the fundamental values are also important for the constitutionalization process. For example, the German Grundgesetz mentions “its responsibility to God and man” in its preamble, and on several occasions also to nature, natural resources, but even more importantly to future generations. The German Federal Constitutional Court has determined in its 2021 ruling that climate protection stems from the fundamental value and the connection with the preamble.

Similarly, Italy, for example, in Article 9 as a fundamental value, in 2022 made amendments, adding that “The Republic protects the environment, biodiversity and ecosystems, also in the interest of future generations”. Following this, judicial and constitutional practice already treats climate stability as part of the common good.

5.5 Green Constitutionalism

The acceptance of climate security as a constitutional matter, from a constitutional-legal perspective, can also be designated as part of the mosaic called “green constitutionalism”. This type of constitutionalism, which arises as a response to new global and security threats (especially in the area of the environment and nature²⁶) is a classic concept of the 21st century, which puts human rights, the environment and security in relation.

To a dominant extent, green constitutionalism is a process that includes the integration of environmental rights and obligations directly into constitutions (or basic laws, as is the case with Germany), as well as a clear recognition that the environment is a fundamental constitutional right, which is linked to human freedoms and rights, health and human development.

This type of constitutionalism is a product of the evolution we are witnessing from a classic constitutionalism (with a focus on political rights, organization of the state, etc.), towards a 21st century constitutionalism that recognizes nature and the environment as constitutional categories and protects them.

Green constitutionalism finds its practical application in Latin America, with the introduction of constitutional provisions in the constitutions of Ecuador (2008) and Bolivia (2009). The Ecuadorian constitution is the first to recognize the rights of nature (*derechos de la naturaleza*), while the Bolivian constitution constitutionalizes the term “Pachamama” (“Mother Earth”) as a living being. The United States and Europe are considered the theoretical cradles of this type of constitutionalism. (Marko Vidaček & Marika Ristovska, 2025, p.97)

²⁶ Although not to that extent, Yugoslavia also experienced some massive environmental damage and catastrophe, especially after the Second World War. In the fifties of the last century, massive pollution of the Vardar River was noticeable, as a result of industrial waste and mines in that area. Later, certain problems will arise with mining in the area of Kosovo and Metohija, where especially coal mines have caused great environmental pollution. The 1970s were also remembered for the pollution of the Danube, which, as one of the largest rivers in Europe, was exposed to a great deal of industrial pollution. This decade and the next (the 80's) also marked the spill of oil in the Adriatic Sea, which has especially actualized the question of protection and strengthening of the marine and coastal ecosystem. For more on the Constitution of the SFRY and the right to a healthy environment from 1974, see Ristovska, Akimovska Maletić and Vidaček (2025).

6. CLIMATE SECURITY CHALLENGES

6.1 Emergence of ecological populism

With the rise of green parties and globalization after 1980, the emergence of ecological, green populism²⁷ is noticeable, which is an approach in which ecology, the environment and climate change are used as a means of mobilizing the masses. Through simple, emotional and "catchy" messages, the government or certain institutions are accused of destroying nature.

This does not necessarily mean a negative phenomenon. The positive side is in the expression of dissatisfaction with anti-environmental and climate change policies, while the negative aspect is in the strengthening of demagoguery, the anti-scientific narrative.

6.2 Instrumentalization of climate security in politics

Just as Sophocles' "Antigone"²⁸ has two choices regarding her brother's death, so too, the issues of climate change, security and justice are unfortunately often posed antagonistically, as irreconcilable opposites. A dominant bloc division is created in the public sphere between pro and anti climate change advocates (and the concepts that come with them), which leads to even greater polarization in society.

Environmental and climate change issues are becoming issues for political debate, with the focus, unfortunately, shifting from the scientific field to social networks.

Climate change has been one of the most controversial topics on a global level for years. Although there is solid evidence of its genesis, manifestation and consequences, some scientists and authors deny the view that it disrupts and negatively affects human security (Simić, 2019, p. 35).

Instrumentalized in this way in daily political discourse, the climate can be used to justify certain economic, social or geopolitical interests, and ultimately turn into blockades and military intervention. This, in turn, raises the question of its militarization.

6.3 Militarization of climate policy

When climate is increasingly accepted as a security issue (and thus constitutionally and legally), following the example of the USA and other countries, it becomes part of military strategies. Climate is becoming an unavoidable part of national security (in addition to the fact that a new concept of climate security is being formed), so it is often given a militaristic²⁹ overtone. If climate events are accepted as a legitimate and rational

²⁷ As stated in the digital dictionary of the Macedonian language, populism is "opportunistic, demagogic politics with influence on the population through an apparent inclination towards the understandings, demands and spiritual needs of the broad masses of the people". As examples of left-wing ecological populism, we can cite Evo Morales in Bolivia and Rafael Correa in Ecuador. As right-wing ecological populism, we can cite Marine Le Pen in France (speaks about the ecology of nations) and Viktor Orbán in Hungary (believes that the protection of Hungarian land from foreign investment is an environmental issue).

²⁸ Antigone in Sophocles' play has to decide whether to respect the imperial decree and leave her brother's corpse unburied (which would mean "yes" to the law, but "no" to the brother) or to decide to bury her brother. She decides to bury him, thus following her moral and religious obligations. In the play, all the main characters suffer as a result of the conflict between law and morality.

²⁹ Militarization (from the Latin *militaris*: military), strengthening of military influence or introduction of a militaristic system. Strengthening militaristic values in society. Similar to militarism: dominance of military ideas, customs and interests, i.e. management of society in

threat, then there is a possibility that such a threat can be resolved through military intervention, rather than through diplomatic or legal means.

When climate events are treated as a threat, there is a danger of military intervention instead of a diplomatic or scientific solution. In the future, a large part of geopolitical actions under the guise of “fighting climate change” may lead to new military interventions.

Therefore, it is of particular importance that a state or international organization will subsume itself under climate security. Its overemphasis, and naturalization of not so natural elements, can easily make sense of the essence of the fight against climate change and serve as an alibi for some other fights. The bad experience of the 19th and 20th centuries can serve as a parallel and an appeal for caution.

6.4 Disproportionality in the effects of climate change

The disproportionate suffering of countries and peoples is one of the greatest challenges related to climate change and climate security. The underdeveloped and most vulnerable countries (especially in Africa, Southeast Asia, Kiribati) are increasingly affected by major droughts, floods, hurricanes. Although they contribute the least to the effects of climate change, they are the most pronounced – negatively. The fact that their resources for prevention, adaptation and other processes are limited further increases their vulnerability.

Especially in terms of economic and social aspects, we have a continuation of the cycle of poverty and insecurity. Therefore, future strategies for combating climate change and accepting climate security must also accept this challenge through mechanisms of international solidarity, followed by financial and technical support for the most vulnerable countries and peoples³⁰.

7. CLIMATE SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF NORTH MACEDONIA

Climate security as a concept in this country is in its infancy. Despite the serious risks from climate disasters and conditions, legal and constitutional obligations still remain incomplete and fragmented.

As for the constitutional order, the constitution does not recognize climate security or this type of threat. However, there are several articles (primarily the fundamental provisions in Article 8 and Article 43 on the environment) that can serve as a basis for the introduction of this type of security in legal practice. In particular, constitutional courts and institutions, by way of a "derivative", can use these articles in a situation of absence.

As for the legal level, the media note that the Climate Action Law has been postponed for 5 years, and it is also noted that there is no National Plan for Adaptation to Climate Change. On the Electronic National Register of Regulations of the Republic of North Macedonia (ENER), it is visible that at the end of 2022, a notice was published to begin the process of preparing a Law on Climate Action, while a version of the draft law was published on 26.01.2023. Although the version does not directly talk about climate

accordance with the values of the military mentality. More: <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/militarizam>

³⁰ Due to the rise in sea levels, a large number of national and cultural minorities may lose their centuries-old habitat. This is especially true for nations or groups like the Caribbean, the Maldives, etc. This also applies to Arctic and subarctic peoples (such as the Inuit, the Saami, the Chukchi), but also to communities around the Ganges or Nile rivers (due to the desertification process).

security, the mention of the terms risks, hazards, and disasters provides a sufficient starting point for strengthening this concept and its greater recognition.

The competent authorities should take urgent and additional measures to deal with climate change, because the country lacks a clearly defined structure, coordination and communication between the parties involved, and a National Adaptation Plan has not yet been adopted, the State Audit Office concluded in its latest report on the country's readiness to face this global challenge, reports the web portal SDK.mk (2024).

However, it is worth noting that certain moves in a positive direction are evident. For example, President Siljanovska Davkova appointed Dr. Vlado Spiridonov, a professor of meteorology and climate change expert, to the Security Council in 2024. It is also important to emphasize that the adoption of the law has the support of the President, while the Government's position is unclear. "I eagerly await the day when I will sign the decree promulgating the Climate Action Law. I believe that this law, which is long overdue, will be a milestone in our climate action", the President stated on October 30, 2024, according to Media.mk (2024)

CONCLUSION

Climate security as a part of environmental security, which focuses exclusively on the damages from climate change and the establishment of a balance, is gaining more and more space in legal and security sciences. The constitutionalization of climate security is a new constitutional challenge in the 21st century.

The paper provides a historical overview of the concept of climate security, which is also accompanied by the process of constitutionalization. Analysing the various constitutional *modus vivendi*³¹, it is concluded that indirect constitutionalization is needed as the most adequate mechanism. The absence of a clearly direct constitutionalization (through new articles or paragraphs), which is not yet known for climate security in its most explicit form, is due to its theoretical and practical incompleteness. Climate security is in a complementary relationship with many similar categories (sustainable development, rights of future generations, rights to nature), and constitutions are not always able to promptly accept such concepts, especially those in development.

The court, in line with living constitutionalism, is obliged to interpret constitutional provisions and fundamental values in relation to the (dis)circumstances around it, and thus introducing climate security into the constitutional-legal framework will enable its existence in the foreseeable future.

The paper states that ecological populism followed by the instrumentalization of climate security, its attempt at militarization and the disproportionality in the effects of climate change are the key challenges towards its future development.

In the Republic of North Macedonia, for example, the constitutional court can easily indirectly constitutionalize climate security by referring to the fundamental values in the constitution and the special article 43. What is missing, however, is greater constitutional-judicial engagement and activity in the Macedonian case. The adoption of the long-awaited Climate Action Law will greatly improve the legal regulation on this issue and will seriously introduce the concept of climate security to a higher level.

³¹ The Latin expression "modus vivendi" translates to "way of living" or "way of coexistence".

REFERENCES

Books / Dissertations

Milosavljević, B. S. (2019). *Security assessment as a factor in the national security strategy of the Republic of Serbia* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Belgrade, Faculty of Political Science.

Udovčić, M. (2024). *Climate diplomacy*. University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science.

Marković, Đ. (2023). *The nature of constitutional court functions* (Doctoral dissertation). University of Belgrade, Faculty of Law.

Journal Articles

Ceranić, V. (2010). Judicial activism and constitutional adjudication: Political implications in a comparative perspective. *Pravnik: Journal for Legal and Social Issues*, 44(88), 131–154.

Koprivnjak, S., & Vidaček, M. (2024). The concepts of environmental security and sustainable development with special reference to national parks. *Security Horizons*, 153–163.

Popović, P. (2014). International climate regime: Realpolitik and climate catastrophe. *Politička Misao*, 51(3), 54–75.

Simić, T. (2019). The impact of climate change on human security in the Republic of Serbia. *Human Security: Student Papers Collection*, 33–43.

Orlović, S. P. (2014). The right to life in the constitution – An ecological angle. *Proceedings of the Faculty of Law in Novi Sad*, 48(4).

Book Chapters / Proceedings

Kijevčanin, R. (2022). *Basic features of constitutional courts in Austria and Italy*. In *Usklađivanje pravnog sistema Srbije sa standardima Evropske Unije* (pp. 281–289). Univerzitet u Kragujevcu.

Vidaček, M., & Ristovska, M. (2025). Green constitutionalism as a contemporary tendency in constitutional law. In *Proceedings of the University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Law* (pp. 83–99). University of Kragujevac.

Ristovska, M., Akimovska Maletić, I., & Vidaček, M. (2025). The Constitution of the SFRY as an indication of the right to a healthy environment in the contemporary Macedonian Constitution. In *Proceedings of the University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Law* (pp. 499–514). University of Kragujevac.

Documents:

United Nations Conference on the Human Environment. (1972). *Declaration of the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (Stockholm Declaration)*. <https://www.un.org/en/conferences/environment/stockholm1972>

United Nations Conference on Environment and Development. (1992). *Rio Declaration on Environment and Development*. <https://www.un.org/en/development/desa/population/theme/agenda-21/rio-declaration>

United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. (2015). *Paris Agreement*. <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/the-paris-agreement>

News / Public Administration Sources

SDK.mk. (2024, December). *Државата не е подготвена за климатските промени: Законот за климатска акција доцни 5 години...* Retrieved January 2025, from <https://sdk.mk/index.php/sakam-zeleno/drzhavata-ne-e-podgotvena-za-klimatskite->

promeni-zakonot-za-klimatska-akcija-dotsni-5-godini-a-nemame-ni-podatotsi-za-emisija-na-gasovi-utvrdi-drzhavniot-revizor/

Media.mk. (2024, October 30). *Претседателката Силјановска Давкова: Со нетрпение го очекувам денот кога ќе го потпишам Законот за климатска акција*. Retrieved January 2025, from

<https://www.media.mk/2024/10/30/%d0%bf%d1%80%d0%b5%d1%82%d1%81%d0%b5%d0%b4%d0%b0%d1%82%d0%b5%d0%bb%d0%ba%d0%b0%d1%82%d0%b0-%d1%81%d0%b8%d1%99%d0%b0%d0%bd%d0%be%d0%b2%d1%81%d0%ba%d0%b0-%d0%b4%d0%b0%d0%b2%d0%ba%d0%be%d0%b2%d0%b0-71/>

Links:

Leksikografski zavod Miroslav Krleža. (n.d.). *Konstitucionalizam*. <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/konstitucionalizam>

Leksikografski zavod Miroslav Krleža. (n.d.). *Militarizam*. <https://www.enciklopedija.hr/clanak/militarizam>

DRMJ – Digital Repository of Media and Journalism. (n.d.). *Populizam*. <http://drmj.eu/show/популизам/м>